

Blattodea including Isoptera

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Carboniferous: *Blattodea* stem group

Phyloblattidae: *Phyloblatta* sp.

Upper Carboniferous
(Virgilian)
New Mexico

Evolution of Folding of the Ano-jugal Lobe in Blattoids

Upper Carboniferous Cockroach: *Phyloblatta* sp

Modern Termite: *Mastotermes*

Carboniferous cockroaches and modern termites fold their ano-jugal lobes in hind wings in the same way.

Hind wings of Orthoneoptera and Blattoneoptera are very different

Orthoneoptera:

- A full anojugal lobe (plesiomorphic) is shared only with the Pleconeoptera.
- ScP long (plesiomorphy)
- ScA long (plesiomorphy)
- Stem of M present (apomorphy, as only in Pleco-M and MP (at length) fused with CuA (apomorphy)
- Stem of Cu absent (plesiomorphy)
- CuP richly branched (plesiomorphy)
- Strut CuA-CuP present (apomorphy)
- This veinal system has several unique plesiomorphic and apomorphic characters.

Blattoneoptera (as also Hemineoptera and Endoneoptera have many similar apo.- and plesio-characters):

- Partial anojugal lobe (apomorphy)
- ScA short, low ridge (apomorphy)
- ScP short (apomorphy)
- Stem of M absent (plesio)
- MA fused at length with R and RP (apo.)
- Short stem of Cu present, CuP often reduced (apo.)
- Strut MP-CuA (arculus) often present (apo.)

See also: Haas and Kukalová-Peck 2001, Dermaptera: structure....

Wing characters indicate the above tree of Neopteran lineages.

ORTHONEOPTERA

PLECONEOPTERA

BLATTONEOPTERA

HEMINEOPTERA

NEOPTERAN HIND WING VEINAL PATTERNS CHARACTERISTIC FOR LINEAGES

Veinal pattern of Orthoneoptera is the most different. Pleconeoptera share with the rest of Neoptera a similar support for anterior wing margin and presence of the cubital stem, while Blattoneoptera & Hemineoptera & Endoneoptera share derived anojugal lobe starting at the anal fold and a long R & MA fusion supporting long wing axis

Cockroaches, termites and their Paleozoic ancestors

Paleozoic Blattoids

Recent Termites

FWs share anal veins ending on the posterior wing margin

HWs share unreduced AA field, and smaller anal lobe, folding flat under HW along the anal fold

Archimylacridae

Mastotermitidae

Recent Blattodea

Periplaneta americana

Recent Blattodea evolved very narrow AA field and much larger, plicate anal lobe

Shared ancestor of cockroaches and termites: Carboniferous blattoids

Fossils: Archimylacridae: *Phyloblatta* sp.

U. Carboniferous
New Mexico

FW: anal veins end on the
posterior wing margin
- as also in Mastotermees

HW: branches on AA veins
are still long, branched
- as also in Mastotermees

Carboniferous blattoids

Carboniferous stem group cockroach *Phyloblatta* sp. differs from Blattodea in having ribbon-like costal area, CuP present, and all anal branches ending on the posterior wing margin. This group folded the hind wings like termites and may be close to termite ancestors. Blattoids share fusion of R to MA supporting the horizontal wing axis with hemipteroids and endopterygotes. Wings suggest that termites probably belong to a separate order (Isoptera).

Carboniferous early cockroach with triangular costal area, but CuP still present and anal branches ending on posterior wing margin. Specimen in Burpee Museum of Natural History, Rockford, Illinois.

HW Blattodea: Blaberidae: *Leucophaea maderae*

Blaberidae: Oxyhaloinae
Rhyparobia madera

FW

Blaberidae: Oxyhaldinae
Rhyparobia madera

FW

SCP
 R &
 MA
 MP
 CulA
 AA1+2

AA3+4

AP

Blaberidae: Oxyhaloinae: *Rhyparobia madera*

HW

HW

Large Cockroach, Ecuador

Blattidae: Blattinae: *Periplaneta americana*

FW

FW Blattidae: Blattinae: *Periplaneta americana*

HW

Blattidae: *Periplaneta americana*

HW Blattidae: *Periplaneta americana*

In Blattodea, AA field always more or less reduced and added to remigium!
 Anal row of sclerites: (AX) fused with (+) (as in Plecoptera)

HW Blattodea: Blattidae: *Periplaneta americana*

Blattodea: Blattidae: *Periplaneta americana*

HW Blattidae: *Periplaneta americana*

J

Blattodea: Diplopteridae: *Diploptera dytiscoides*

HW

AA 3+4 clearly joins remigium!

Blattodea: Diplopteridae: Plectopterinae: *Plectoptera* sp

HW

Cu stem very short

AP

FW Mastotermitidae: *Mastotermes darwiniensis*

All anal branches run toward posterior wing margin, as in the Paleozoic (but not modern) Blattodea

Mastotermitidae *Mastotermes darwiniensis*

Important: stem of M absent,
MA fused basally to RP

FW Mastotermitidae: *Mastotermes darwiniensis*

CuP reduced but claval line sometimes sclerotized

Anal veins end on posterior wing margin – as in the Paleozoic ancestral cockroaches

Termites are closer to ancestral cockroaches than are the modern Blattodea

HW Mastotermitidae: *Mastotermes darwiniensis*

Important: true stem of M (MA & MP) absent; instead, RP & MA is fused while MP is adjacent to them ventrally.

In Orthoptera the stem of M is present (as apomorphy). Hence blattoids and orthopteroids cannot be sister groups.

HW Mastotermitidae: *Mastotermes darwiniensis*

HW Polyphagidae: Polyphaginae: *Polyphaga aegyptica*

FW Polyphagidae: Polyphaginae: *Polyphaga aegyptica*

ScA ridge

CuP often reduced, sometimes runs in claval line

AD

AA3+4

Blattodea

Polyphagidae: *Polyphaga aegyptica*

HW

Blattodea: Polyphagidae: *Polyphaga saussurei* (Dohrn)

HW

Polyphagidae: *Polyphaga sausseri* (Dohrn)

FW

Blattodea: Polyphagidae: *Polyphaga saussurei*

FW

ONLY AA₁₊₂ branches
sim at claval line!

HW Polyphagidae: *Polyphaga saussurei*

Blattodea

Polyphagidae: *Polyphaga aegyptica*

HW

